

ADMINISTRATORS' MANAGERIAL COMPETENCIES FOR SUSTAINABLE HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN SECONDARY EDUCATION IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The inability of teachers to timely cover the scheme of work, students' truancy and persistent lateness to school, poor attitude towards teaching and learning, activities of cultism and frequent conflicts among secondary school students in Enugu State prompted this study to determine the administrators' managerial competencies for sustainable human resource management in secondary education in Enugu State. Two specific purposes were formulated and two research questions guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study population comprised all the 291 secondary school principals' in Enugu State. Simple random sampling technique was used to sample 146 principals for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a 19 items researchers' developed instrument titled; "Administrators' Managerial Competencies for Sustainable Human Resource Management Questionnaire (AMCSHRMQ). The face validation of the instrument was established by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy and one from the Department of Educational Foundations (Measurement and Evaluation Unit), Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The Cronbach alpha was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. Coefficient value of 0.71 was obtained. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Findings of the study revealed among others that secondary school administrators lack managerial competencies for students' human resource management by not providing counseling services to students regarding their learning process, providing incentives' for students' to increase their motivation to learn among others. Based on the finding, it was recommended among others that student human resource management should be incorporated and emphasized in the training guide for educational administrators in order to make them

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develop more suitable students centered policies in their various schools. Conclusion was drawn based on the findings.

Keywords: administrators, managerial competencies, sustainable human resource management

1. Introduction

The desire to achieve a functional education system is widely spread among stakeholders in the education industry. This cannot be easily achieved without a progressive and effective management of personnel by administrators in the school system. The chief administrator in secondary school is the principal who is entrusted with numerous managerial responsibilities. In support of this, Akinfolarin (2017) asserted that at the secondary level of education, the principal is the chief executive officer of the school who is responsible for effective management of school resources for the actualization of stated goals and objectives. Nkwoh (2011) observed that school principals must possess a wide array of competencies in order to lead schools effectively towards the accomplishment of educational goals, which has led to changing expectations of what leaders need to know and must be able to do. Competency as opined by Carol and Edward (2004) is the successful performance of a task through the use of knowledge, skills, attitude and judgment. Competency is the ability and skills required to accomplish given tasks or roles. School administrators must acquire competencies in managing the vital assets in their various schools to achieve desirable outcome. Effective managerial competency of school administrators is central to turning the school around. Management is the arrangement of available human and material resources for the achievement of desired goals and objectives (Nwune, Nwogbo & Okonkwo, 2016). It is the effective and judicious utilization of organization resources for goals attainment. Human beings are instrumental in the successful realization of sustainable development in any organization. Effective management of people will not only increase productivity but will equally ensure goals accomplishment. According to Nnebedum and Egboka (2017), human resource is the personnel embodied with knowledge, skills and expertise in education production process. They are the people that work along with other resources in order to achieve desired results in organization. In line with this, Ekanem (2014) asserts that meaningful educational value change can take place in individual human beings' who are involved in the management of the educational system for sustainable growth. Human resource is a tool for transforming the goals and objectives of the school system into reality. No meaningful change can take place without the human factor. Human resource is a vital asset in the hand of the administrator that must be well managed in order to drive organizational growth. School administrator is required to acquire numerous managerial competencies having effective human resource management as his central focus. Providing management support services and regulating the activities of staff and students is central to human resource management in the school system.

Migrating from the traditional pattern of managing people in organization known as personnel management comes the human resource management which focuses on effectiveness, culture, productivity and employee's participation. In the view of Ofojebe and Nnebedum (2016), human resource management involves assessing the need of staff, satisfying the need, disciplining and controlling staff to enhance the attainment of school goals and objectives. It is the appropriate use of personnel to achieve both organization goals and individual goals as well. Human resource management sees people as valuable resources for achieving desired output. Human resource management as summarized by Armstrong (2004) is a strategic approach to the acquisition, motivation, development and management of the organization's human resources. Heathfield (2011) sees it has the function within an organization that focuses on recruitment of, management of, and providing direction for the people who work in the organization. School administrators have a key role to play in sustaining effective management of people in the school. Heller (2012) outlined the functions of school administrators to include; management of instructional programmes, staff personnel administration, students' personnel administration, finance and physical resource management and community relationship management. The school principal perform varying leadership roles which include; training and development of personnel, overseeing staff needs, providing students personnel services, and creating a conducive teaching and learning climate among others. Human resource management function of school administrators involve staffing, supervision, motivation, staff appraisal, staff professional development, communication, and discipline as well as students management. According to Akinfolarin (2017), there are two areas of human resource management in the school system; the staff human resource management and the students' human resource management. Emphasis is placed on teachers in human resource management with less focus on the students. To have a complete human resource management function in school, both staff and students must be a central focus.

Staff human resource management in school involves the overall activities and functions embraced to enhance workers' productivity. Workers in schools are the academic and non-academic staff who continuously strive to accomplish the desired goals and objectives of the school system. The effective management of teachers and auxiliary staff will help to ensure better output. Workers need adequate motivation and good welfare policies at work to increase their performance. Welfare policy does not only include money, but other packages such as employer and employee interpersonal relationship, as it is often times geared towards the enrichment of personnel performance (Akinfolarin, 2017). Also, training and ensuring professional development of teachers through seminars, workshops, conferences and research engagement will further boost their job performance. Workers should be acquainted with change and innovation in the education industry for better result. This can be realized through effective supervision. Segun cited in Okoye, Onyali and Ezeugbor (2016) highlights the essence of supervision in the area of teachers' professional development and the processes that must be followed to achieve the desired educational objectives. School

administrators should also engage in encouraging workers participation in decision making and delegating tasks to subordinates in order to make them have the sense of being part of the school. However, irrespective of the usefulness of delegation to organization success, some school heads still find it difficult to delegate functions to their subordinates. Similarly, Akinfolarin (2017) observed that some school heads avoid delegating certain duties to their assistants due to the fear of their jobs being overtaken by subordinates which may amount to delay in tasks completion. School administrator should acquire competencies in tasks delegation, providing staff and students support services, and applying appropriate disciplinary actions against misconducts for sustainable human resources management of staff and students in the school.

Like every other organizations, the school has students as its product. They are key stakeholder in the school system in which the performance of the school is measured. Similarly, Emetarom cited in Nwakpa (2015) noted that schools are set up not for teachers, not for parents, not for educational administrators but for students. It is sad that despite students being the key factor in the school system, most of them have been neglected to face hardship, victimization, social conflicts and delinquencies. Student human resource management is not only the function of the school head but all stakeholders in the school system. It is an indispensable core and functional task of the school principal and his teachers and even non tutorial staff (Nwakpa, 2015). School administrators must strive to provide the necessary atmosphere to enable students realize their learning goals and objectives. Outstanding students should be rewarded at the end of every academic session in order to ignite their interest in learning. Similarly, Onyali and Akinfolarin (2017) noted that students' feeling of being rewarded for outstanding academic performance increases their motivation and zeal for better performance. Student human resource management function centers on ensuring; students enrolment, motivation, suitable welfare packages, safety measures, discipline, counseling services, participation, incentives, conducive learning climate among others. Also, school heads should provide inclusive education by protecting the interest of all students which include; male and female, physically challenged, gifted, talented, children of low income earners, and students with mental retardation among others. All forms of students' personnel services should be appropriately rendered to various categories of students in order to have an inclusive education. School heads must acquire competencies and required skills in the quest to have a sustainable human resource management in the school.

The concept of sustainable development has assumed much relevance not only to environmental and biodiversity issues but also to education practice (Akpan & Onabe, 2016). Change and sustainable development occur in the education sector just like every other sector. There are emerging trends in all aspects of the education enterprise which requires educational managers to adapt to this changing environment for sustainability. Many school administrators are yet to acclimatize with the digitalized and modern pattern of school management. Sustaining effective human resource management in secondary education is imperative towards the realization of educational goals.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Resources are transformational tools in the hands of administrators which must be well managed for better returns on investment. However, Nigeria being a developing nation is still battling with numerous challenges in her education sector ranging from bad leadership, poor resources management competencies, conflicts, inadequate funding and poor educational policies among others. These challenges may differ from one State to another. Personal observation by the researchers revealed the cases of teachers' absenteeism, inability to timely cover the scheme of work, some non-teaching staff sleeping on duty and gossiping, students' truancy and persistent lateness to school, poor attitude towards learning, cult practices and frequent conflicts among secondary school students in Enugu State. Perhaps, this problem may be as a result of school administrators' incompetency to effectively carry out their managerial functions for the sustenance of effective management of their human resources in the school. It is against this premise that this study aimed at determining the administrators' managerial competencies for sustainable human resource management in secondary education in Enugu State is conceived.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the administrators' managerial competencies for sustainable human resource management in secondary education in Enugu State.

Specifically, the sought to determine:

1. Administrators' managerial competencies for staff human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State
2. Administrators' managerial competencies for students' human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State.

1.3 Research Questions

1. What are the administrators' managerial competencies for staff human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State?
2. What are the administrators' managerial competencies for students' human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State?

2. Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design which sought to collect data on the opinions of the participants. The study was conducted in Enugu State. The study population comprised all the 291 secondary school principals' in Enugu State. Simple random sampling technique was used to sample 146 principals for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a 19 items researchers' developed instrument titled; "Administrators' Managerial Competencies for Sustainable Human Resource Management Questionnaire (AMCSHRMQ). The instrument was structured on a four points rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly

Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The face validation of the instrument was established by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy and one from the Department of Educational Foundations (Measurement and Evaluation Unit), Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The suggestions and inputs of the experts were reflected on the final draft of the instrument. Cronbach alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. Coefficient value of 0.71 was obtained which indicated that the instrument was reliable. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed by the researchers together with six research assistants who were briefed on how to distribute and retrieve the copies of the instrument. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The mean response were adjudged on the following basis that any mean score of 2.50 and above is taken to indicate agreement while any mean score that falls below 2.50 is taken as disagreement.

3. Results

Research Question 1: What are the administrators' managerial competencies for staff human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation scores of administrators' managerial competencies for staff human resource management

S/N	Items	$\bar{X}$	SD	Decision
1.	Ensuring timely communication with staff	2.57	0.53	Agree
2.	Involving staff in decision making	2.22	0.84	Disagree
3.	Delegating of tasks to subordinates in order to give them sense of responsibility	2.59	0.45	Agree
4.	Proving disciplinary measures to check staff misconducts in school	3.34	0.16	Agree
5.	Providing teachers' incentives to increase their motivation at work	2.49	0.94	Disagree
6.	Appraising staff in order to improve their job performance	2.56	0.30	Agree
7.	Organizing orientation for new staff on school activities and goals	2.34	0.22	Disagree
8.	Organizing training and workshops for professional advancement of teachers	2.25	0.55	Disagree
9.	Promoting teachers' welfare to increase their commitment to instructional tasks	2.98	0.75	Agree
10.	Supervising teachers' in order to render professional guidance.	3.25	0.21	Agree
Mean of means and Standard Deviation		2.66	0.50	Agree

Table 1 revealed that some respondents agreed while others disagreed on some items on administrators' managerial competencies for staff human resource management.

Generally, the mean of means' value of 2.66 falls above 2.50 indicating agreement on administrators' managerial competencies for staff human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State. The standard deviation indicates that the items mean responses are close to one another, showing that the items are homogeneous.

Research Question 2: What are the administrators' managerial competencies for students' human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation scores of administrators' managerial competencies for students' human resource management

S/N	Items	$\bar{X}$	SD	Decision
11.	Providing counseling services for students regarding their learning process	1.22	0.33	Disagree
12.	Creating measures to ensure students safety	2.56	0.45	Agree
13.	Ensuring appropriate students' discipline in the school	3.01	0.12	Agree
14.	Providing incentives' for students' to increase their motivation to learn	1.69	0.94	Disagree
15.	Carrying out periodic enrolment of students	3.11	0.40	Agree
16.	Assigning leadership roles to students in school to encourage their participation	2.51	0.88	Agree
17.	Organizing orientation for new students' on school activities	1.25	0.45	Disagree
18.	Implementing good students welfare policies	2.18	0.55	Disagree
19.	Supervising students' activities in order to render professional guidance.	2.57	0.22	Agree
Mean of means and Standard Deviation		2.23	0.48	Disagree

Table 2 revealed that some respondents agreed while others disagreed on some items on administrators' managerial competencies for students' human resource management. Generally, the mean of means' value of 2.23 falls below 2.50 indicating disagreement on administrators' managerial competencies for students' human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State. The standard deviation scores for all the items in the cluster are within the same range, indicating that the respondents are homogeneous in their responses.

4. Discussion

Findings on Table 1 revealed that majority of the respondents agreed on some items on their managerial competencies for staff human resource management by ensuring timely communication with staff, delegating of tasks to subordinates in order to give them sense of responsibility and providing disciplinary measures to check staff misconducts in the school. Others include; appraising staff in order to improve their job performance, promoting teachers' welfare to increase their commitment to instructional

tasks, and supervising teachers' in order to render professional guidance. Others disagreed on some items on their competencies for staff human resource management. Generally, the mean of means' value of 2.66 falls above 2.50 indicating agreement on administrators' managerial competencies for staff human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State. This is similar to Nnebedum and Egboka's (2017) finding which revealed that secondary school principals in Enugu State have adequately adopted human resource management strategies such as involving staff in decision making process, issuing query to erring staff, supervising teachers' classroom instructional delivery, praising staff for excellent performance, monitoring staff truancy level to encourage school attendance. However, the variation is that this study covers students' human resource management which their study did not.

Findings on Table 2 revealed that majority of the respondents disagreed on some items on their managerial competencies for students human resource management by not providing counseling services to students regarding their learning process, providing incentives' for students' to increase their motivation to learn, organizing orientation for new students' on school activities, and not implementing good students welfare policies while others agreed on some items on their competencies for students human resource management. Generally, the mean of means' value of 2.23 fall below 2.50 indicating disagreement on administrators' managerial competencies for student human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State. This is in agreement with Akpan and Onabe (2016) who enthused that despite the efforts of some stakeholders, yet the problem of managing student personnel services (student human resource management) effectively to enhance sustainable secondary education still persists.

5. Conclusion

Staff and students are the human resources in the school that produces educational outcomes. Sustaining their interests and aspirations will reduce tension and unnecessary conflict in the school thus, promotes school developmental plan. However, based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that administrators' do not have managerial competencies for students' human resource management in secondary schools in Enugu State. The study also concluded that secondary school administrators' have managerial competencies for staff human resource management in Enugu State.

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Secondary school administrators should strive to balance their competencies on staff human resource management for sustainability in the aspects of involving staff in decision making, providing teachers' incentives to increase their motivation at work, organizing orientation for new staff on school activities and

goals, organizing training and workshops for professional advancement of teachers.

2. Student human resource management should be incorporated and emphasized in the training guide for educational administrators in order to make them develop more suitable students centered policies in their various schools.

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